

MENTAL HEALTH and MINDFULNESS

mentortec

DISCOVER-IN
Innovation at your hands

**ORGANKITS
DUCA ABRUZZI
LIBERO GRASSI**

MENTAL HEALTH and MINDFULNESS

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SCIENCE

TECHNOLOGY

ENGINEERING

ART

**MATHS
PHYSICS**

**PHYSICAL
Education**

SCIENCE

- ✓ Brain anatomy
- ✓ Synapses and neurotransmitters
- ✓ Propagation of the nerve impulse
- ✓ Processing of information
- ✓ Sensory perception

TECHNOLOGY

HEALTH BRAIN MONITORING

- ✓ PET: Positron emission tomography
- ✓ EEG: Electroencephalography
- ✓ MEG: Magnetoencephalography
- ✓ SPECT: Tomoscintigraphy
- ✓ fMRI: Functional magnetic resonance imaging

ENGINEERING

- ✓ Algorithms
- ✓ Artificial Neural Network
- ✓ Artificial Intelligence

ART

- ✓ Learning systems facilitated through the union of verbal, iconic and sound languages
- ✓ Arnheim: theory of “pure visibility”. Shapes and colours’ effects on brain areas.
- ✓ Relationship between sounds and colours
- ✓ Mondrian’s Abstract Art
- ✓ How fragmented language affects attention and concentration disorders.

MMATHS & PHYSICS

- ✓ Brain physics
- ✓ Electrical circuits
- ✓ Processing of information
- ✓ Measurement of brain activity
- ✓ Magnetic field generated by brain activity
- ✓ Neuron as a current dipole

PHYSICAL Education

- ✓ How regular workout affects brain health and its functioning
- ✓ Workout and BDNF(brain-derived neurotrophic factor) synthesis
- ✓ Benefits of fitness, joga and autogenic training on mental health
- ✓ Nutrition and food supplement as a support to psycho-physical and emotional wellness

CONSORTIUM

“The brain has no wrinkles: if it continues to work hard, it is constantly renewed, even after 80 years and, unlike other organs, it can even improve”

Rita Levi Montalcini

 OrganKits
for STEAM

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